

Biological properties of the Honey Bee products

Introduction to Lifestyle Diseases

In the modern era, lifestyle diseases have reached alarming levels, becoming a key global health crisis. Lifestyle diseases also referred to as non-communicable diseases (NCDs), are long-term health problems principally caused by unhealthy lifestyles like improper diet, lack of physical activity, excessive smoking, alcohol consumption, and prolonged stress (Craig et al., 2023). In contrast to illnesses caused by pathogens, lifestyle diseases evolve gradually due to behavioral and environmental effects that significantly affect public health, economic stability, and quality of life. Obesity, cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), type 2 diabetes, respiratory conditions, and specific cancers are among the most prevalent lifestyle diseases. These diseases are nowadays responsible for an important portion of global mortality, predominantly in developed and rapidly industrializing countries. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), NCDs interpretation for nearly 71% of all deaths worldwide, with cardiovascular diseases being the leading cause of death, followed by cancers and respiratory diseases (Sahin et al., 2022).

The shift in disease patterns is closely linked to rapid urbanization, changing dietary habits, and a more sedentary lifestyle. Traditional diets rich in fruits, vegetables, and whole grains have been largely replaced by processed foods high in refined sugars, unhealthy fats, and salt (Mozaffarian, D., 2016). Simultaneously, advancements in technology have reduced physical activity, both at work and in daily life, contributing to rising rates of obesity and metabolic disorders. Intensifying the issue, lifestyle diseases often develop slowly and asymptotically, making early detection challenging. By the time symptoms emerge, the diseases may have already progressed to advanced stages, making treatment more difficult and costly. Moreover, lifestyle diseases often co-occur, with conditions like obesity and diabetes

increasing the risk of heart disease, stroke, and other complications (Dubois et al., 2015). Figure 1 shows some common lifestyle diseases.

Figure 1. Common lifestyle diseases.

Despite the challenges posed by lifestyle diseases, they are largely preventable. Simple lifestyle modifications—such as adopting a balanced diet, engaging in regular physical activity, avoiding smoking and excessive alcohol, and managing stress—can significantly reduce the risk of developing these conditions (Mozaffarian et al., 2012). Public health initiatives to raise awareness, promote healthy behaviours, and improve healthcare infrastructure are crucial to reversing the rising tide of lifestyle diseases. In this context, understanding the factors that contribute to lifestyle diseases, as well as effective prevention and management strategies, has become increasingly important (Samuel et al., 2024). This introduction sets the stage for a deeper exploration of the complex interplay between lifestyle, disease, and health outcomes, emphasizing the need for both individual and societal interventions to combat the hidden global crisis of lifestyle diseases.

Types of Lifestyle Diseases

Lifestyle diseases encompass a wide range of chronic conditions that arise due to unhealthy lifestyle choices. While there are many forms of these diseases, the most prevalent and impactful include:

1. Obesity

Obesity is a condition characterized by excessive body fat that increases the risk of various health problems, including CVDs, diabetes, and certain cancers. The rise in obesity rates worldwide is a direct consequence of:

- Overconsumption of high-calorie, nutrient-poor foods
- Physical inactivity
- Poor sleep patterns
- High stress levels

Obesity is often the precursor to other lifestyle diseases, creating a cycle of chronic illness (Egger et al., 2014).

2. Cardiovascular Diseases (CVDs)

Cardiovascular diseases are a group of disorders affecting the heart and blood vessels, leading to conditions like heart attacks, strokes, and hypertension. These diseases are closely linked to lifestyle factors such as:

- Poor diet (high in saturated fats, refined sugars, and salt)
- Lack of physical activity
- Smoking
- Excessive alcohol consumption

- Chronic stress

CVDs are the leading cause of death globally, largely driven by the rising incidence of obesity, sedentary lifestyles, and unhealthy eating habits (Barbaresko et al., 2018).

3. Type 2 Diabetes

Type 2 diabetes occurs when the body becomes resistant to insulin or does not produce enough insulin to regulate blood sugar levels effectively. Unlike type 1 diabetes, which is an autoimmune condition, type 2 diabetes is strongly influenced by lifestyle factors such as:

- Obesity, particularly abdominal fat
- Sedentary behavior
- Unhealthy diet (high in processed foods and sugary drinks)

Unchecked, diabetes can lead to complications such as nerve damage, kidney failure, vision loss, and an increased risk of heart disease (Kolb et al., 2017).

4. Chronic Respiratory Diseases

Chronic respiratory diseases, such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma, are long-term conditions that affect the airways and lungs. These diseases are aggravated by lifestyle factors, including:

- Smoking (the leading cause of COPD)
- Exposure to environmental pollutants
- Occupational hazards (e.g., dust and chemical inhalation)

While genetics play a role, lifestyle choices like smoking cessation and reducing exposure to pollutants can significantly lower the risk (Senapati et al., 2015).

5. Cancers

Certain types of cancer have been closely linked to lifestyle factors. These include cancers of the lung, colon, breast, and liver. Contributing lifestyle factors are:

- Smoking (responsible for lung cancer and other cancers)
- Unhealthy diet (high in processed meats and low in fiber)
- Excessive alcohol consumption
- Physical inactivity
- Obesity

Cancer prevention strategies emphasize lifestyle changes, including quitting smoking, reducing alcohol intake, and maintaining a healthy diet and weight (Balwan et al., 2021).

6. Liver Diseases

Liver diseases, particularly non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), have become increasingly common as a result of lifestyle factors. NAFLD is characterized by excess fat accumulation in the liver, unrelated to alcohol consumption, and is often associated with:

- Obesity
- Type 2 diabetes
- Insulin resistance
- High cholesterol

If left untreated, NAFLD can progress to liver inflammation, fibrosis, and cirrhosis, increasing the risk of liver cancer (Vachliotis et al., 2022).

7. Metabolic Syndrome

Metabolic syndrome is a cluster of conditions—including high blood pressure, high blood sugar, abnormal cholesterol levels, and excess body fat around the waist—that occur together and increase the risk of heart disease, stroke, and type 2 diabetes. Lifestyle factors contributing to metabolic syndrome include:

- Poor diet
- Physical inactivity
- Obesity

Managing metabolic syndrome requires a holistic approach involving dietary changes, increased physical activity, and weight management (Lemieux et al., 2020).

8. Osteoporosis

Osteoporosis is a condition characterized by weakened bones, increasing the risk of fractures. While genetics play a role, lifestyle factors like diet and physical activity are critical in its development. Contributing factors include:

- Lack of weight-bearing exercise
- Insufficient calcium and vitamin D intake
- Excessive alcohol consumption
- Smoking

Maintaining a diet rich in calcium, engaging in regular physical activity, and avoiding smoking and excessive drinking can help prevent osteoporosis (Mahadik et al., 2021).

9. Mental Health Disorders

While not always considered a "lifestyle disease," mental health disorders such as depression, anxiety, and stress-related illnesses are strongly influenced by lifestyle factors. These conditions are often exacerbated by:

- Chronic stress
- Poor diet
- Lack of physical activity
- Substance abuse (alcohol and drugs)

The mind-body connection underscores the importance of a balanced lifestyle in maintaining mental well-being and preventing the onset or worsening of mental health conditions (Firth et al.,2020).

10. Kidney Disease

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is another condition closely linked to lifestyle factors. Risk factors for CKD include:

- High blood pressure
- Type 2 diabetes
- Obesity
- Poor diet high in salt and unhealthy fats

CKD can lead to kidney failure and necessitate dialysis or a kidney transplant. Managing the underlying lifestyle factors is essential for preventing and slowing disease progression.

The range of lifestyle diseases is vast, and they are often interrelated, with one condition increasing the risk of developing others. These diseases are not only preventable but often manageable through simple lifestyle changes, including a balanced diet, regular physical

activity, smoking cessation, and reducing alcohol intake. Public awareness and proactive healthcare interventions are critical in curbing the rise of lifestyle diseases and promoting healthier living (Neale et al., 2023).

Obesity: A Major Link in Causing Lifestyle Diseases

Obesity has emerged as one of the most significant public health challenges worldwide, acting as a key contributor to numerous other lifestyle diseases. Defined by an excessive accumulation of body fat, obesity is often measured by body mass index (BMI), with a BMI of 30 or higher classified as obese. The rise in global obesity rates is driven by changes in dietary habits, sedentary lifestyles, and environmental factors (Nyberg et al., 2018). Obesity is not just a condition in itself but a central link to the development of other major lifestyle diseases, creating a vicious cycle of chronic illness and health complications. The root causes of the lifestyle diseases are mentioned in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Root causes of lifestyle diseases

1. Obesity and Cardiovascular Diseases (CVDs)

Cardiovascular diseases, including heart disease, stroke, and hypertension, are closely associated with obesity. Excess body fat, particularly visceral fat around the abdomen, contributes to several mechanisms that increase cardiovascular risk:

- **Atherosclerosis:** Obesity promotes the buildup of fatty plaques in the arteries, leading to atherosclerosis (hardening of the arteries), which can cause heart attacks and strokes.
- **Hypertension:** Obesity increases blood pressure by raising blood volume and resistance in the blood vessels. This increased pressure strains the heart, leading to hypertension, a major risk factor for heart disease.

- **Dyslipidemia:** Obesity often causes an imbalance in lipid levels, increasing low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol and triglycerides while reducing high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol. This contributes to the development of atherosclerosis and other cardiovascular conditions (Powell-Wiley et al., 2021).

2. Obesity and Type 2 Diabetes

Type 2 diabetes is one of the most well-established consequences of obesity. Excess fat, especially in the abdominal area, leads to insulin resistance, a condition in which the body's cells become less responsive to insulin. As a result:

- **Insulin Resistance:** Obesity is a primary driver of insulin resistance, leading to high blood sugar levels and eventually, the development of type 2 diabetes.
- **Pancreatic Strain:** The pancreas overworks to produce more insulin to compensate for the body's insulin resistance. Over time, this leads to pancreatic beta-cell dysfunction, further exacerbating diabetes.

The connection between obesity and diabetes is so strong that the term **diabesity** is often used to describe the combination of both conditions, which increases the risk of cardiovascular disease, kidney disease, and other complications (Leitner et al., 2017).

3. Obesity and Cancer

Obesity is a recognized risk factor for several types of cancer, including cancers of the breast, colon, pancreas, liver, and kidney. The mechanisms linking obesity to cancer include:

- **Chronic Inflammation:** Obesity is associated with a chronic low-grade inflammatory state. Adipose (fat) tissue produces inflammatory cytokines, which can promote tumor growth and cancer progression.

- **Hormonal Imbalances:** Obesity alters the levels of hormones such as estrogen, insulin, and insulin-like growth factors (IGFs), which can promote cell proliferation and inhibit cell death, increasing the risk of cancer development.
- **Oxidative Stress:** Excess fat can contribute to oxidative stress, leading to DNA damage and mutations that may result in cancer (Nunez et al., 2017).

4. Obesity and Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD)

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is strongly linked to obesity and is characterized by the accumulation of fat in the liver. NAFLD can progress to more serious liver conditions such as:

- **Non-Alcoholic Steatohepatitis (NASH):** A more severe form of NAFLD, where liver inflammation and damage occur, potentially leading to fibrosis and cirrhosis.
- **Liver Cancer:** Chronic liver inflammation associated with NASH can increase the risk of liver cancer.

NAFLD is often referred to as the hepatic manifestation of metabolic syndrome, which is driven by obesity, insulin resistance, and dyslipidemia (Wong et al., 2018).

5. Obesity and Respiratory Disorders

Obesity contributes to a range of respiratory disorders, with obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) being one of the most common. Other respiratory conditions exacerbated by obesity include asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD).

- **Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA):** Excess fat around the neck and chest can block airways during sleep, leading to episodes of stopped breathing. OSA is strongly linked to obesity, and it increases the risk of heart disease, stroke, and high blood pressure.

- **Asthma:** Obesity-related inflammation may worsen asthma symptoms, and studies show a higher prevalence of asthma in obese individuals (Peters et al., 2018).

6. Obesity and Osteoarthritis

Obesity significantly increases the risk of osteoarthritis, especially in weight-bearing joints like the knees and hips (Figure 3). The extra weight puts mechanical stress on joints, accelerating the breakdown of cartilage, which leads to:

- **Joint Degeneration:** The additional pressure on joints from excess body weight increases wear and tear, contributing to the development and progression of osteoarthritis.
- **Inflammation:** Obesity also triggers the release of inflammatory molecules that can exacerbate joint damage and pain, worsening the symptoms of osteoarthritis (Palazzo et al., 2016).

Figure 3. Obesity induced Osteoarthritis disease

7. Obesity and Mental Health Disorders

Obesity has a bidirectional relationship with mental health disorders (Figure 4). On one hand, obesity increases the risk of depression and anxiety; on the other, individuals with these conditions may be more prone to weight gain due to factors like emotional eating and reduced physical activity.

- **Depression:** The psychological and social stigma of obesity can lead to low self-esteem, poor body image, and depression. Additionally, the inflammation associated with obesity is thought to play a role in the development of depressive symptoms.
- **Anxiety:** Obesity can also exacerbate anxiety, particularly social anxiety, due to body image concerns and reduced mobility (Kim et al., 2020).

Figure 4. Obesity relationship with mental health disorders.

8. Obesity and Hypertension

Hypertension, or high blood pressure, is commonly linked to obesity (Figure 5). The relationship between the two conditions is driven by multiple factors, including increased blood volume, arterial stiffness, and hormonal changes associated with fat tissue.

- **Increased Blood Volume:** Obesity increases the overall volume of blood circulating in the body, placing additional pressure on the arterial walls.
- **Renal Function:** Obesity can impair kidney function, leading to increased fluid retention and higher blood pressure.

Obesity acts as a central hub in the development of many lifestyle diseases, amplifying the risk and severity of conditions such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, cancer, and more. Its multifactorial impact—through inflammation, hormonal imbalances, insulin resistance, and mechanical strain—makes it a critical target for public health interventions. Preventing and managing obesity through lifestyle changes, such as healthy eating, regular physical activity, and behavior modification, is key to reducing the burden of associated lifestyle diseases and improving overall health outcomes (Leggio et al., 2017).

Figure 5. The relationship between the Obesity with Hypertension.

Role of Key Enzymes and Hormones in Lifestyle Diseases

The enzymes and hormones mentioned play crucial roles in various physiological processes, and their dysregulation can contribute to the development and progression of lifestyle diseases. These diseases, influenced by factors such as poor diet, physical inactivity, and stress, often involve metabolic imbalances, inflammation, and organ dysfunction. Below is an overview of how each enzyme or hormone is linked to lifestyle diseases:

1. HMG-CoA Reductase

Function: HMG-CoA reductase is a key enzyme in the cholesterol synthesis pathway, catalyzing the conversion of HMG-CoA to mevalonate, a precursor to cholesterol (Takei et al., 2020).

Link to Lifestyle Diseases:

Cardiovascular Diseases: Overactivity of this enzyme leads to increased cholesterol synthesis, particularly low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol, contributing to atherosclerosis and increasing the risk of heart disease and stroke.

Therapeutic Target: Statins, a class of drugs widely used to lower cholesterol levels, work by inhibiting HMG-CoA reductase.

2. Ghrelin

Function: Ghrelin is a hormone produced by the stomach that stimulates appetite and promotes fat storage. It is often referred to as the "hunger hormone."

Link to Lifestyle Diseases:

Obesity: Elevated ghrelin levels can lead to increased appetite and weight gain, contributing to obesity, which is a major risk factor for diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and metabolic syndrome.

Diabetes: Ghrelin may also influence insulin secretion and sensitivity, affecting glucose metabolism (Abizaid., 2019).

3. Leptin

Function: Leptin is a hormone produced by fat cells that regulates energy balance by inhibiting hunger. It signals to the brain that the body has sufficient energy stored in fat (Izquierdo et al., 2019).

Link to Lifestyle Diseases:

Obesity: In obesity, leptin levels are often elevated, but individuals develop leptin resistance, meaning the brain does not respond to leptin's signal, leading to overeating and further weight gain.

Metabolic Syndrome: Leptin resistance is associated with insulin resistance and metabolic dysregulation, contributing to the development of metabolic syndrome, type 2 diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases (Engin., 2017).

4. Troponin

Function: Troponin is a protein involved in muscle contraction, particularly in the heart. It is released into the bloodstream during heart muscle damage.

Link to Lifestyle Diseases:

Cardiovascular Diseases: Elevated levels of troponin in the blood are a key biomarker for heart attacks and other cardiac events. Troponin levels are used to diagnose myocardial

infarctions and monitor heart damage in conditions like heart failure and chronic ischemic heart disease (Huang et al., 2021).

5. Angiotensin

Function: Angiotensin is a peptide hormone that plays a central role in regulating blood pressure by causing blood vessels to constrict and by stimulating the release of aldosterone, which increases sodium and water retention.

Link to Lifestyle Diseases:

Hypertension: Overactivity of the renin-angiotensin system (RAS), which produces angiotensin II, leads to high blood pressure. Chronic hypertension is a major risk factor for heart disease, stroke, and kidney disease.

Therapeutic Target: ACE inhibitors and angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs) are commonly used to lower blood pressure by inhibiting the action of angiotensin II (Rasha et al., 2019).

6. Alpha-Amylase

Function: Alpha-amylase is an enzyme responsible for breaking down carbohydrates (starch) into simpler sugars, such as maltose and glucose.

Link to Lifestyle Diseases:

Obesity and Type 2 Diabetes: Increased alpha-amylase activity can lead to rapid digestion of carbohydrates, causing spikes in blood sugar levels, which contributes to insulin resistance and the development of type 2 diabetes. Over time, this process promotes obesity and metabolic syndrome (Mojbafan et al., 2017).

7. Alpha-Glucosidase

Function: Alpha-glucosidase is an enzyme that breaks down complex carbohydrates into glucose in the small intestine.

Link to Lifestyle Diseases:

Diabetes: By increasing postprandial (after-meal) blood glucose levels, alpha-glucosidase contributes to poor glucose control in type 2 diabetes. Alpha-glucosidase inhibitors (e.g., acarbose) are used as a treatment to slow carbohydrate absorption and reduce blood sugar spikes in diabetic patients (Kato et al., 2020).

8. CYP17 (Cytochrome P450 17A1)

Function: CYP17 is an enzyme involved in steroid hormone biosynthesis, including the production of androgens and estrogens.

Link to Lifestyle Diseases:

Hormone-Related Cancers: Abnormal CYP17 activity can contribute to the development of hormone-sensitive cancers, such as prostate cancer and breast cancer, by altering the levels of androgens and estrogens. CYP17 inhibitors are used in the treatment of certain types of cancer to reduce hormone production (Santoso et al., 2023).

9. SOD2 (Superoxide Dismutase 2)

Function: SOD2 is an antioxidant enzyme that converts superoxide radicals (a type of reactive oxygen species) into hydrogen peroxide and oxygen, reducing oxidative stress in cells.

Link to Lifestyle Diseases:

Cardiovascular Diseases: Reduced SOD2 activity increases oxidative stress, contributing to endothelial dysfunction, atherosclerosis, and heart failure.

Cancer: Oxidative stress due to low SOD2 activity can also promote DNA damage, increasing the risk of cancer development (Kachur et al., 2017).

10. Matrix Metalloproteinases (MMPs)

Function: MMPs are a group of enzymes that break down extracellular matrix proteins, playing a role in tissue remodeling and inflammation.

Link to Lifestyle Diseases:

Cancer: Overexpression of MMPs, particularly MMP-2 and MMP-9, is associated with tumor invasion and metastasis in various cancers by breaking down the extracellular matrix, allowing cancer cells to spread.

Cardiovascular Diseases: MMPs contribute to the degradation of the extracellular matrix in blood vessels, promoting plaque instability in atherosclerosis, which can lead to heart attacks and strokes (Mirica et al., 2022).

11. Elastase

Function: Elastase is a protease enzyme that breaks down elastin, a key component of the extracellular matrix in connective tissues.

Link to Lifestyle Diseases:

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD): Overactivity of elastase, particularly neutrophil elastase, leads to the breakdown of lung tissue, contributing to the development of emphysema, a form of COPD. Elastase activity is exacerbated by smoking and chronic inflammation.

Atherosclerosis: Elastase can also degrade elastin in blood vessels, contributing to vascular stiffening and the progression of atherosclerosis (Ali et al., 2018).

12. Collagenase

Function: Collagenase is an enzyme that breaks down collagen, a major structural protein in connective tissue.

Link to Lifestyle Diseases:

Osteoarthritis: Overexpression of collagenase contributes to the breakdown of collagen in joints, leading to cartilage degradation and joint inflammation seen in osteoarthritis.

Cancer: Collagenase facilitates tumor invasion by breaking down the collagen barrier surrounding tumors, allowing cancer cells to spread to other tissues.

These enzymes and hormones play critical roles in various physiological processes, and their dysregulation is often central to the development of lifestyle diseases. From obesity and diabetes to cancer and cardiovascular diseases, understanding the role of these biomolecules helps in identifying therapeutic targets and interventions to manage and prevent these conditions. Lifestyle modifications, such as healthy eating, regular exercise, and stress management, can help regulate enzyme and hormone activity, mitigating the risk of lifestyle diseases.

Lifestyle diseases, such as diabetes, hypertension, obesity, cardiovascular diseases, and metabolic syndrome, are a growing global health concern driven by sedentary habits, unhealthy diets, and chronic stress. These conditions often require long-term pharmacological interventions to manage symptoms, prevent complications, and improve quality of life. While conventional medications have proven efficacy, they are often accompanied by side effects, drug resistance, and issues of patient compliance, which highlight the need for alternative or complementary approaches, such as natural supplements, to address these health challenges holistically (Ling et al., 2024).

Medicines for Lifestyle Diseases and Their Side Effects

Medications play a vital role in managing lifestyle diseases by targeting specific biological pathways. For instance, in diabetes, drugs like metformin improve insulin sensitivity, while sulfonylureas stimulate insulin release (Rapoliene et al., 2024). In hypertension, ACE inhibitors and beta-blockers help regulate blood pressure. Statins are frequently prescribed to manage high cholesterol, and anticoagulants are used to prevent clot formation in cardiovascular conditions. However, these medications often come with significant side effects:

- **Diabetes Medications:** Metformin may cause gastrointestinal discomfort and vitamin B12 deficiency, while insulin therapy can lead to weight gain and hypoglycemia.
- **Hypertension Medications:** ACE inhibitors can cause a persistent dry cough, and diuretics may result in electrolyte imbalances and dehydration.
- **Cardiovascular Drugs:** Statins can induce muscle pain and liver enzyme elevations, and anticoagulants carry a high risk of bleeding.
- **Obesity Medications:** Drugs like orlistat can lead to gastrointestinal issues, while GLP-1 receptor agonists might cause nausea and vomiting.

While these medications are essential for disease management, their adverse effects can significantly impact patient adherence and overall well-being. Long-term use may also lead to tolerance, reduced efficacy, and the necessity for higher doses or additional drugs, further increasing the risk of side effects (Dhara et al., 2024).

The Need for Alteration Through Natural Supplements

The limitations of conventional medicines, there is a growing interest in natural supplements as an alternative or complementary approach to managing lifestyle diseases. Supplements derived from natural sources, such as propolis, curcumin, omega-3 fatty acids,

and herbal extracts, offer bioactive compounds with fewer side effects and can address underlying mechanisms such as oxidative stress, chronic inflammation, and metabolic dysregulation. These supplements can help reduce dependence on synthetic medications and mitigate their side effects while providing additional health benefits (Chen et., 2022).

Natural supplements often need to be altered or tailored for individual needs due to variability in their composition, bioavailability, and patient responses. For example, propolis' chemical composition varies depending on its botanical source, which can influence its efficacy. Similarly, certain herbal supplements may interact with conventional medications, requiring dosage adjustments. Alterations may also be necessary to optimize the delivery method, such as converting raw extracts into capsules or tinctures for better absorption (Poddar et al., 2019).

Incorporating natural supplements into a treatment plan requires careful consideration, including clinical validation, standardization, and monitoring to ensure safety and effectiveness. The integration of these supplements can complement pharmacological treatments, improve patient compliance, and provide a more holistic approach to managing lifestyle diseases.

In conclusion, while conventional medicines are indispensable for managing lifestyle diseases, their side effects and limitations underscore the need for alternative strategies. Natural supplements offer a promising avenue for holistic disease management, requiring thoughtful alterations and integration to maximize their benefits and enhance patient outcomes. This approach aligns with the growing trend toward personalized and sustainable healthcare solutions.

Propolis as an Alternative Supplement for Lifestyle Diseases

Propolis, often referred to as "bee glue," is a resinous, sticky substance produced by honey bees from plant resins, mixed with beeswax and their own enzymes. Bees use propolis to seal and protect their hives, but its potential for human health has been recognized for centuries in traditional medicine systems around the world. Rich in bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, phenolic acids, essential oils, and terpenoids, propolis has drawn scientific interest for its therapeutic properties. These include antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, immunomodulatory, and anticancer effects, which make it a promising natural supplement for managing lifestyle diseases (Alvarenga et al., 2021).

Lifestyle diseases, including diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular diseases, obesity, and metabolic syndrome, have become a global health crisis due to sedentary lifestyles, unhealthy diets, and environmental stressors. Conventional medications, while effective, often come with side effects and limitations. Propolis, as a natural supplement, offers a complementary approach to addressing these diseases by targeting their underlying mechanisms, such as oxidative stress, chronic inflammation, and metabolic dysregulation (Zulhendri et al., 2021).

Propolis is particularly notable for its antioxidant properties, attributed to its high concentration of flavonoids and phenolic compounds. These antioxidants neutralize free radicals, which are implicated in the onset and progression of many chronic diseases. Additionally, its anti-inflammatory effects help suppress the chronic low-grade inflammation that underpins conditions like atherosclerosis, diabetes, and obesity. Propolis has also demonstrated antidiabetic effects, including improving insulin sensitivity, regulating blood glucose levels, and protecting pancreatic β -cells from oxidative damage. For cardiovascular health, propolis aids in improving lipid profiles by lowering LDL cholesterol and enhancing HDL cholesterol, while also supporting endothelial function and reducing blood clot risks (Sajjadi et al., 2023).

As an adjunct in obesity management, propolis has shown potential in modulating fat metabolism by inhibiting the formation of new fat cells (adipogenesis) and promoting fat breakdown (lipolysis). Furthermore, its immunomodulatory properties help bolster the immune system, which is often compromised in individuals with chronic conditions. Its neuroprotective effects also make it a candidate for reducing the risk of cognitive decline associated with diseases like diabetes and hypertension (El-Sehrawy et al., 2024).

Despite its promising benefits, the use of propolis as a supplement for lifestyle diseases is not without challenges. The chemical composition of propolis varies depending on its botanical source, geographic origin, and season, making standardization difficult. Additionally, some individuals may experience allergic reactions, particularly those sensitive to bee products. Interactions with conventional medications, such as anticoagulants and antihypertensives, also warrant caution. Further research is needed to establish standardized dosages, delivery methods, and clinical efficacy (Nazari-Bonab et al., 2024).

In conclusion, propolis holds significant potential as a natural, bioactive supplement for managing lifestyle diseases. Its multifaceted therapeutic properties provide a holistic approach to addressing the underlying mechanisms of these conditions, offering an alternative or complementary option alongside conventional treatments. With more clinical studies and standardization efforts, propolis could become an integral part of the preventive and therapeutic landscape for lifestyle-related health challenges.

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION:

Apidae is a family of insects that includes stingless bees, honeybees, and other specialized groups. Honeybees are a large group of social insects that are more specifically, best-known domesticated species used in modern beekeeping. These honey bees produce and

maintain a variety of bee products in their hives that can be beneficial to human health. Without a doubt, honey – a complex combination of nutrients and bioactive compounds with a variety of biological activities is the best-known and most popular product produced by honeybees (1-7). In addition to honey, honeybees can also produce a variety of other products, such as propolis, bee pollen, bee bread, royal jelly, and beeswax. These products are a combination of pollen grains, nectar, resin, and mixture of enzymes secreted by honeybees. Several studies have demonstrated the positive health effects of these natural products on humans, suggesting that they could be used as active ingredients in pharmaceuticals (8) Among these bee products, Propolis is a natural antibiotic produced by honeybees. Bees collect the sap from needle-leaved timber or evergreens and mix their very own discharges and bee wax with the sap and they create a sticky greenish-brown product that is covered by bees inside the hive for defending the bees and the colony from moisture, wind, and microbes (9) (Simone- Finstrom and Spivak, 2010). Propolis is purported to have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antidiabetic, and even anti-neoplastic activity. The health benefits of propolis and honey are well known. People have used propolis for a variety of purposes since ancient times, especially in folk medicine to treat various diseases. Because the Egyptians were familiar with the putrefactive properties of bee glue, they used it to embalm their dead. Propolis was used by the Incas as a fever reducer. Greek and Roman physicians prescribed it in wound treatment as a topical therapy for skin and mucous membrane wounds and as an antiseptic and healing product (10).

METHODOLOGY:

1.Preliminary Qualitative Analysis

1.1. Test for Alkaloids

a. Mayer' s test

To a few ml of plant sample extract, two drops of Mayer's reagent was added along the sides of test tube. Appearance of white creamy precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids [6].

b. Wagner's test

A few drops of Wagner's reagent was added to few ml of plant extract along the sides of test tube. A reddish- Brown precipitate confirms the test as positive [7].

1.2. Test for Amino acids

The extract (100 mg) was dissolved in 10 ml of distilled water and filtered through Whatmann No. 1 filter paper and the filtrate was subjected to test for Amino acids.

a. Ninhydrin test

Two drops of ninhydrin solution (10 mg of ninhydrin in 200 ml of acetone) was added to 2 ml of aqueous filtrate. Appearance of purple colour indicates the presence of amino acids. [8]

1.3. Test for Carbohydrates

a. Molish' s test

To 2 ml of plant sample extract, two drops of alcoholic solution of α - naphthol were added. The mixture was shaken well and few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid was added slowly along the sides of test tube. A violet ring indicates the presence of carbohydrates.

b. Benedict' s test

To 0.5 ml of filtrate, 0.5 ml of Benedict's reagent was added. The mixture was heated on a boiling water bath for 2 minutes. A characteristic-coloured precipitate indicates the presence of sugar.

1.4. Test for Fixed oils and Fats

a. Spot test

A small quantity of extract was pressed between two filter papers. Oil stain on the paper indicates the presence of fixed oils.

b. Saponification test

A few drops of 0.5 N alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution was added to a small quantity of extract along with a drop of phenolphthalein. The mixture was heated on a water bath for 2 hours. Formation of soap or partial neutralization of alkali indicates the presence of fixed oils and fats [9].

1.5. Test for Glycosides

For 50 mg of extract was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid for 2 hours on a water bath, filtered and the hydrolysate was subjected to the following tests

a. Borntrager's test

To 2 ml of filtered hydrolysate, 3 ml of chloroform was added and shaken, chloroform layer is separated and 10% ammonia solution was added to it. Pink colour indicates presence of glycosides[6].

b. Legal's test

50 mg of extract is dissolved in pyridine, sodium nitroprusside solution was added and made alkaline using 10% NaOH. Presence of glycoside was indicated by pink colour.

1.6. Test for Phenolic compounds and Tannins

a. Ferric Chloride test

The extract (50 mg) was dissolved in 5 ml of distilled water. To this few drops of neutral 5% ferric chloride solution was added. A dark green colour indicates the presence of phenolic compound.[10]

b. Gelatin test

The extract (50 mg) was dissolved in 5 ml of distilled water and 2 ml of 1% solution of Gelatin containing 10% NaCl was added to it. White precipitate indicates the presence of phenolic compounds.[6]

c. Lead acetate test

The extract (50 mg) was dissolved in of distilled water and to this 3 ml of 10% lead acetate solution was added. A bulky white precipitate indicates the presence of phenolic compounds.

d. Alkaline reagent test

An aqueous solution of the extract was treated with 10% ammonium hydroxide solution. Yellow fluorescence indicates the presence of flavonoids.

e. Magnesium and Hydrochloric acid reduction

The extract (50 mg) was dissolved in 5 ml of alcohol and few fragments of magnesium ribbon and concentrated hydrochloric acid (drop wise) were added. If any pink to crimson colour develops, presence of flavanol glucosides is inferred.[11]

1.7. Test for phytosterols

a. Liebermann-Burchard's test

The extract (50 mg) was dissolved in of 2 ml acetic anhydride. To this, 1 or 2 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid was added slowly along the sides of the test tube. An array of colour change shows the presence of phytosterols.[12]

8. Test for Proteins

The extract (100 mg) was dissolved in 10 ml of distilled water and filtered through Whatmann No. 1 filter paper and the filtrate was subjected to test for proteins.

a. Millon's test

To 2 ml of filtrate few drops of Millon's reagent are added. A white precipitate indicates the presence of proteins.[13]

b. Biuret test

2 ml of filtrate was treated with 1 drop of 2% copper sulphate solution. To this 1 ml of ethanol (95%) was added, followed by excess of potassium hydroxide pellets. Pink colour ethanolic layer indicates the presence of protein. [14]

1.9. Test for Saponins

The extract (50 mg) was diluted with distilled water and made up to 20 ml. The suspension was shaken in a graduated cylinder for 15 minutes. A two cm layer of foam indicates the presence of saponins. [9]

1.10. Test for gum and Mucilages

The extract (100 mg) was dissolved in 10 ml of distilled water and to this 2 ml of absolute alcohol was added with constant stirring. White or cloudy precipitate indicates the presence of Gums and Mucilages. [15]

1.11. Test for volatile oil

For volatile oil estimation 50 mg of powdered material (crude drug) was taken and subjected to hydro- distillation. The distillate was collected in graduate tube of the assembly, wherein the aqueous portion automatically separated out from the volatile oil [16].

2. Qualitative and quantitative Analysis

Qualitative and quantitative analysis of phytochemicals can be done using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy (GCMS). GCMS can be applied to solid, liquid and gaseous samples. First the samples were converted into gaseous state then analysis was carried out on the basis of mass to charge ratio.

2.1. Gas Chromatography

Gas chromatography was applicable for volatile compounds. In this method, species distribute between a gas and a liquid phase. The gas phase was flowing and the liquid phase was stationary. When the sample molecules were in the liquid phase, they were stationary. The rate of migration depends on how much of the chemical species was distributed into the liquid phase. The higher the percentage of material in the gaseous states faster the migration. The species which distributes itself 100% in the stationary state will not migrate. If a sample distributes itself in both phases, it will migrate at an intermediate rate. This gas chromatography gives the total amount of vapour. Thus, it is most widely used for quantitative analysis.

4.2.2 FT-IR

The Propolis sample was placed in the sample holder, Spectra was registered using the Infinity spectrophotometer at a range of 500-4000 cm^{-1} at a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} , registering 64 scans.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

1. Preliminary Qualitative Analysis

S.No	Metabolite	Test performed	Observation	Result	Figure No.
1	Alkaloids	+Mayer's reagent	Presence of Cream color ed precipitate	+	1
		+Dragendorff's reagent	Presence of reddish-brown precipitate	+	2

2	Flavonoids	Alkalinetest	Intense yellow color with dil.NaOH that turns color less on Adding dil.HCl	+	3
		+H ₂ SO ₄	Presence of reddish orange color	+	4
		+leadacetate	Presence of white precipitate	+	5
		Shinodatest	Presence of crimson Pink color	+	6
3	Sterols (Liebermann test)	+CHCl ₃ +Acetic anhydrid e+ Conc.H ₂ S O ₄	Presence of a reddish-brown ring	+	7
4	Terpenoids (Liebermannstest)	+CHCl ₃ +Acetic anhydride+ Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Absence of green color	-	
5	Anthraquinone (Borntrager's test)	+FeCl ₃ +Conc.HCl +diethylether +Ammonia	Absence of reddish-orange color	-	
6	Anthocyanin	HClTest	No Color change	-	
		+2%Ninhydrin	Absence of Purple color	-	

7	Proteins	reagent			
		+2%CuSO ₄ + 95%ethanol+K OH pellet	Absence of blue color	-	
		+conc.HNO ₃	Presence of Yellow coloration	+	8
8	Phenoli c compoun ds	+5%neutralFeCl ₃	Presence of a bluish-green colored solution	+	9

METABOLITE	OBSERVATION	RESULT
<p style="text-align: center;">Test for Alkaloids</p>		<p style="text-align: center;">++</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Test for Flavonoids</p>		<p style="text-align: center;">++</p>

<p>Sterols (Liebermann test)</p>		<p>++</p>
<p>Proteins</p>		<p>++</p>
<p>Phenolic compounds</p>		<p>++</p>

<p>Carbohydrates</p>	<p>The image shows two test tubes labeled 'EPE'. The left tube is labeled 'Molisch test' and contains a reddish-brown liquid. The right tube is labeled 'Fehling's test' and contains a dark blue liquid with a reddish-brown precipitate at the bottom.</p>	<p>++</p>
<p>Tannin</p>	<p>The image shows a test tube labeled 'EPE' containing a yellowish liquid. Below the tube is a label 'Gelatin test'.</p>	<p>+</p>
<p>Cardiac glycosides</p>	<p>The image shows two test tubes labeled 'EPE'. The left tube is labeled 'Bi₂O₃ Water' and contains a yellowish liquid with a reddish-brown precipitate at the bottom. The right tube is labeled 'Keller-Kiliani test' and contains a dark brown liquid.</p>	<p>++</p>

2 GC-MS analysis to identify the compounds in Propolis

Gas Chromatography- Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) chromatogram of ethanol extract of Propolis showed 40 peaks, which reflects the presence of 40 phytochemical compounds. Out of them 10 compounds were identified as major compounds are shown in table 4.2.1(a). The gas chromatogram of Propolis confirmed the presence of various compounds with different retention times as illustrated in table 4.2.1(a). These compounds were identified through mass spectrometry compounds and their peak area(%), retention time, molecular formula, molecular weight and their biological activity related with medicinal uses are given in table 4.2.1(a) and the structure of the compounds are given in the table 4.2.1 (b)

Chromatogram of GCMS analysis indicates the most of the extracted compounds of Propolis were saturated and unsaturated fatty acids (organic compounds) and organo metallic compounds and alkanes. Biological activity of chemical compounds present in Propolis confers antioxidant, antimicrobial activity that includes antifungal, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, and anti-parasitic activities on Propolis as shown in the table 4.2.1(a)

The biomolecules given in table 4.2.1(a) contains high affinity in mitigation of chemotherapy side effects, ability to modulate cardiovascular diseases, arthritis due to the presence of anti-inflammatory property. Ethanol extract of propolis contains antimicrobial property that has high potential to fight against the harmful microorganism and pathogens which tend to cause various diseases

Antibacterial function of propolis sample fights against the both harmful gram-positive and gram negative bacteria Propolis also exhibit antiviral activity that is capable of treating Herpes Simple Virus both in vitro and in vivo.

An ethanolic extract of propolis is high in flavonoid Chrysin constituents numerous biological property that includes antitumour, anti-diabetic property Antimicrobial property Anti-allergic property antioxidant property

GC-MS Analysis- Propolis**CHROMATOGRAM**

S. No.	COMPOUND NAME	PEAK AREA (%)	Retained Time	Molecular Formula	Molecular weight (g/mol)
01	Phenylethyl Alcohol	0.33	7.842	C8H10O	122.16
02	1,2-Benzenediol	0.40	8.998	C6H6O2	110.11
03	Hydroquinone	0.40	8.998	C6H6O2	110.11
04	Benzofuran, 2,3-dihydro-	0.54	9.364	C8H8O	120.15
05	Benzene, 1-ethynyl-4-fluoro-	0.54	9.364	C8H5F	120.12
06	Acetic acid, 2-phenylethyl ester	0.47	9.786	C10H12O2	164.2
07	Acetamide, 2-chloro-N-phenethyl-	0.47	9.786	C10H12ClNO	197.66
08	Acetamide, N-(2-phenylethyl)-	0.47	9.786	C10H13NO	163.22
09	Benzeneacetic acid	0.48	9.920	C8H8O2	136.15
10	Acetic acid	0.48	9.920	C2H4O2	60.05
11	2-Methoxy-4-vinylphenol	0.69	10.731	C9H10O2	150.17
12	ortho-Methoxyacetophenone	0.69	10.731	C9H10O2	150.17
13	Thymol	0.69	10.731	C10H14O	150.22
14	1 2-(2-Hydroxy-2-phenylethyl)-3,5,...	1.55	12.386	C15H18N2O	242.32
15	2,3-Dimethylanisole	1.55	12.386	C9H12O	136.19

16	Seychellene	0.41	12.708	C15H24	204.35
17	1H-Benzocycloheptene, 2,4a,5,6,7...	0.41	12.708	C15H24	204.35
18	2,5-Dimethylbenzyl chloride	0.47	12.819	C9H11Cl	154.63
19	Benzene	0.47	12.819	C6H6	78.11
20	cis-.alpha.-Bisabolene	0.36	13.686	C15H24	204.35
21	1H-Benzocycloheptene	0.36	13.686	C15H24	204.35
22	Diethyl Phthalate	0.54	14.241	C12H14O4	222.24
23	2-Naphthalenemethanol	0.52	14.852	C11H10O	158.2
24	Naphthalene	0.52	14.852	C10H8	128.169
25	delta.-Selinene	0.52	14.852	C15H24	204.35
26	5-Hexen-3-ol, 2,3-dimethyl-	0.48	15.319	C8H16O	128.21
27	Pregnan-18-oic acid, 20,20- [1,2-...	0.48	15.319	C24H38O4	390.6
28	2,2-Diethoxytetrahydrofuran	0.70	15.408	C8H16O3	160.21
29	Butanoic acid	0.70	15.408	C4H8O2	88.11
30	Allyl dithioisobutyrate	0.70	15.408	C7H12S2	160.3
31	Thiophene, tetrahydro-2- methyl-	0.71	15.497	C5H10S	102.2
32	alpha.-D-Xylofuranoside, methyl...	0.71	15.497	C6H12O5	164.16
33	D-Fructose, 3-O-methyl-	0.66	15.563	C7H14O6	194.18
34	(Methylthio)-acetonitrile	18.25	16.063	C3H5NS	87.15
35	Ethane, isothiocyanato-	18.25	16.063	C3H5NS	87.15

36	n-Hexadecanoic acid	9.65	18.252	C16H32O2	256.42
37	Oleic Acid	1.02	19.896	C18H34O2	282.5
38	cis-Vaccenic acid	1.02	19.896	C18H34O2	282.5
39	6-Octadecenoic acid	1.02	19.896	C18H34O2	282.5
40	Pentadecanoic acid	7.29	20.129	C15H30O2	242.4
41	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid	0.33	20.352	C18H32O2	280.4
42	1-Heptadecanol, acetate	0.33	20.352	C19H38O2	298.5
43	9H-Fluoren-9-imine	0.47	22.140	C13H9N	179.22
44	Acridine	0.47	22.140	C13H9N	179.22
45	2-Propen-1-one	9.45	22.296	C3H4O	56.06
46	8-Methyl-4-azafluorene, phenylimine	9.45	22.296	C19H14N2	270.3
47	3H-Indol-3-one, 2-[(1,2- dimethyl...	6.03	22.985	C16H20N2O	256.339
48	Indan, 1-methyl-	0.40	23.151	C10H12	132.2
49	Dinaphtho[1,2-b:1',2'-d]furan	11.45	23.829	C20H12O	268.3
50	4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 5- hydroxy...	11.45	23.829	C27H32O14	580.5
51	Retinal, 9-cis-	2.70	24.096	C20H28O	284.4
52	Coumaran-6-ol-3-one	2.70	24.096	C16H12O4	268.26
53	Propenone	2.70	24.096	C15H12O4	256.25
54	Chrysin	6.43	24.518	C15H10O4	254.24
55	1(2H)-Naphthalenone	2.53	24.751	C10H8O	144.17
56	7,8-Diethylbenz[a]anthracene	2.53	24.751	C22H20	284.4

57	4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 3,5,7-tri...	6.31	24.884	C18H16O5	312.3
58	8-Methyl-4-azafluorene, phenylimine	6.31	24.884	C19H14N2	270.3
59	4',5-Dihydroxy-7- methoxyflavanone	1.18	25.084	C16H14O5	286.28
60	2-Propen-1-one, 1-(2,4- dihydroxy...	1.18	25.084	C15H12O4	256.25
61	Estra-1,3,5(10)-trien-17-one, 2,...	1.18	25.084	C18H22O2	270.4
62	1,2- Bis(trimethylsilyl)benzene	0.54	26.306	C12H22Si2	222.47
63	Pyridine, 4-ethenyl-	0.48	27.095	C7H7N	105.14
64	4-Cyanobenzophenone	0.48	27.095	C14H9NO	207.23
65	Acetic acid, oxo((1- phenylethyl)...	0.48	27.095	C44H60N6O9	817
66	4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 5,7- dihyd...	0.35	27.506	C20H20O5	340.4
67	2-Ethylacridine	0.35	27.506	C15H13N	207.27
68	p-Bis(p- methoxyphenyliminomethyl...	0.35	27.506	C22H20N2O2	344.4
69	dl.-alpha.-Tocopherol	0.53	27.651	C29H50O2	430.7

1) Benzene, 1-(1,5-dimethyl-4-hexenyl-4-methyl)

2) Thiophene, tetrahydro-2-methyl-(Methylthio)-acetonitrile

3) Hexadecanoic acid

4) Octadecanoic acid

5) Pentadecanoic acid

6) 2-Propen-1

7) 4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 2,3-dihydro,7-dihydroxy-2-phenyl-, (S)

8) Dinaphtho[2,1-b:1',2'-d]furan

9) Retinal

10) Chrysin

Table 2.1 (b) Chemical Structure of Compounds Present in Propolis

S.NO	COMPOUND	STRUCTURE
1.	Benzene, 1-(1,5-dimethyl-4-hexenyl-4-methyl)	
2.	Thiophene, tetrahydro-2-methyl-(Methylthio)-acetonitrile	
3.	Hexadecanoic acid	
4.	Octadecanoic acid	

5.	Pentadecanoic acid	
6.	2-propen-1	
7	4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 2,3-dihydro,7-dihydroxy-2-phenyl-, (S)	
8	Dinaphtho[2,1-b:1',2'-d]furan	
9	Retinal	
10	Chrysin	

Commercial propolis extract consists of flavanoids with high antioxidant activity. This results the new possibility of preferring propolis in inhibiting the elastase enzyme.

3.FTIR

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) is a vital tool (FTIR spectrum over a suitable range, typically from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1}) for characterizing the chemical composition of propolis, a resinous substance collected by honeybees. FTIR spectra provide detailed information about the functional groups present in the sample based on their vibrational transitions. Based on the provided FTIR spectrum of propolis, the characteristic peak and its corresponding functional groups are listed as follows:

Fig :FTIR Spectra of Propolis (EPE)

Peak in cm^{-1}	Functional group
3309.85 cm^{-1}	Broad peak indicative of O-H stretching vibrations, typical for hydroxyl groups found in phenolic compounds and alcohols.

2970.38 cm ⁻¹ 2885.51 cm ⁻¹	Peaks corresponding to C-H stretching vibrations of aliphatic hydrocarbons (methyl and methylene groups).
1928.82 cm ⁻¹	This peak was less common in organic compounds but could be associated with overtones or combination bands.
1643.35 cm ⁻¹	C=O stretching vibration, characteristic of carbonyl groups such as those in esters, ketones, or aldehydes. This peak may also overlap with C=C stretching vibrations in aromatic compounds.
1381.03 cm ⁻¹	Bending vibrations of C-H bonds in alkanes (methyl groups).
1334.74 cm ⁻¹ 1273.02 cm ⁻¹	These peaks can be attributed to C-O stretching vibrations in ethers, esters, or carboxylic acids.
1165.00 cm ⁻¹	C-O-C stretching vibrations, typically found in ethers or esters.
1087.85 cm ⁻¹ 1049.28 cm ⁻¹	C-O stretching vibrations, common in alcohols, ethers, or esters.
879.54 cm ⁻¹	This peak was often associated with out-of-plane bending vibrations of C-H bonds in aromatic rings.
802.39 cm ⁻¹	C-H out-of-plane bending vibrations, indicating aromatic compounds.

555.50 cm ⁻¹	Possibly related to bending vibrations involving heavy atoms (such as in aromatic compounds or poly substituted aromatics).
519.29 cm ⁻¹ 457.97 cm ⁻¹	These peaks were less common but could indicate bending vibrations in larger molecular structures or specific inorganic components if present.
438.70 cm ⁻¹ 408.91 cm ⁻¹	Similar to the previous peaks, these were likely associated with bending vibrations or specific structural features.

The FTIR spectrum of propolis indicates the presence of several key functional groups which includes the following,

- Hydroxyl groups (O-H): The broad peak was observed at 3309.85 cm⁻¹, common in phenolic compounds and alcohols, which were common in propolis.
- Aliphatic hydrocarbons (C-H): Peaks at 2970.38 cm⁻¹ and 2885.51 cm⁻¹.
- Carbonyl groups (C=O): Sharp peak at 1643.35 cm⁻¹, indicating presence of flavonoids, esters, ketones, or aldehydes.
- Aromatic compounds (C=C and C-H): Peaks around 1381.03 cm⁻¹, 879.54 cm⁻¹, and 802.39 cm⁻¹. This confirms the presence of aromatic rings, which are characteristic of many bioactive compounds in propolis.
- C-O stretching vibrations: Peaks at 1273.02 cm⁻¹, 1165.00 cm⁻¹, 1087.85 cm⁻¹, and 1049.28 cm⁻¹, indicating the presence of ethers, esters, or carboxylic acids.

These functional groups were consistent with the known composition of propolis, which includes phenolic compounds, flavonoids, esters, and aromatic compounds. This spectrum provides a comprehensive understanding of the chemical makeup of the propolis sample analysed. The results and implications include,

- **Bioactive Components:** The presence of phenolic and flavonoid compounds can be linked to the antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties of propolis.
- **Quality Control:** FTIR can be used to assess the quality and authenticity of propolis samples by comparing spectra with known standards.
- **Product Development:** Understanding the chemical composition helps in developing propolis-based products with specific health benefits.

Therefore, this has provided an overall understanding of the compounds present and its implication providing insights into its bioactive compounds and potential health benefits.

As a result, this has given us a general grasp of the substances there and their implications, giving us information about their bioactive components and their health advantages.

The combination of qualitative testing, FTIR, and GC-MS data provides an extensive overview of propolis as a rich source of bioactive compounds. The qualitative analysis demonstrates the variety of beneficial compounds present, and the comprehensive profiles provided by GC-MS and FTIR confirm the detailed profiles of these compounds, their roles and quantities. According to both qualitative and quantitative tests, propolis has a high concentration of flavonoids and phenolic components, which was consistent with its potent antibacterial and antioxidant properties (Bankova, V 2005). The anti-inflammatory and antibacterial qualities are further supported by the presence of terpenoids and other volatile chemicals. Overall, the combination of various analytical techniques validates the traditional

medical applications of propolis and suggests potential for further applications in nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals.

Conclusion:

Phytochemical analysis, both qualitative and quantitative, is essential for understanding the chemical composition and potential therapeutic benefits of Propolis. Qualitative methods helps to identify the presence of different classes of compounds, while quantitative methods measure their exact concentrations.

Propolis consisting of plant exudates, buds and resins implies that the vegetation type directly influences its chemical composition. Apart from widely studied phenols and flavonoids, alkaloids were the most abundant phytochemicals with noticeable effects on the bioactivities of propolis samples. Proteins, Phenolic compounds, Carbohydrates, Tannin and Cardiac glycosides were also abundant in the propolis, and they influenced the antibacterial activities of propolis.

GC-MS and FT-IR analysis can be used to screen bioactive compounds in propolis as it results in different compounds in the propolis samples, and propolis is a rich source of biologically active compounds. The bioactivities of propolis are ascribed to the presence of reported compounds, Benzene, 1-(1,5-dimethyl-4-hexenyl-4-methyl), Thiophene, tetrahydro-2-methyl-(Methylthio)-acetonitrile, Hexadecanoic acid, Octadecanoic acid, Pentadecanoic acid, 2-propen-1, 4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 2,3-dihydro,7-dihydroxy-2-phenyl-, (S), Dinaphtho[2,1-b:1',2'-d]furan, Retinal, Chrysin which are phytochemicals identified through GC-MS and FT-IR analysis.

Chapter 2

Introduction:

“Metabolic syndrome” (MetS) is a cluster of components that reflect over nutrition, a sedentary lifestyle, and resulting excessive obesity. These factors significantly increase the risk of developing obesity, diabetes, heart disease, and hypertension (1). The metabolic syndrome is closely associated with a "Westernized" lifestyle that is defined by an abundance of high-fat foods and a lack of physical activity that leads to obesity (2). Obesity is an energy imbalance between calories consumed and calories expended. The accumulation of more calories results in excessive body fat. Several possible mechanisms lead to obesity due to changes in dietary supplements and physical activities (3). An increase in Body Mass Index (BMI) results in non-communicable diseases linked with increased mortality. These include cardiovascular diseases, Diabetes, Musculoskeletal disorders, polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) in women, and certain types of cancers (4). The risk of these non-communicable diseases increases with an increase in BMI.

Energy homeostasis is associated with obesity which causes significant disturbances in endocrine function induced by food consumption (5). Hormonal interaction between Ghrelin and Leptin plays an important role in appetite regulation. Leptin regulates the food intake and energy consumption to maintain BMI on a long-term basis (6). Ghrelin is a hunger-stimulating hormone that is produced in the gut it is also referred to as “Hunger hormone” it increases the appetite take in more calories and store fat (7). Studies suggest that abdominal fat causes fat cells to release ‘pro-inflammatory’ chemicals, which can make the body less sensitive to the insulin it produces by disrupting the function of insulin-responsive cells and their ability to respond to insulin and leading to insulin resistance –type 2 diabetes (8). Improper interaction between Ghrelin and Leptin may result in hyperlipidemia which refers to the high amount of lipid present in blood resulting in Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL). An increase in LDL decreases the level of High-Density Lipoprotein (HDL). HDL plays an essential role in cholesterol homeostasis. It is involved in the transfer of cholesterol from extra-hepatic tissues

to the liver (9). LDL is referred to as Bad Cholesterol because it hardens the cholesterol due to increased free fatty acid (FFA) which accumulates triglycerides (TG), this leads to increased hepatic synthesis of very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) the entry of LDL in bloodstreams clogs the arteries that leads to stroke or heart attack (10).

Obesity, a common and important factor of the PCOS phenotype, has increased over the past two decades. The prevalence of PCOS has increased only slightly and not significantly. These results suggest that obesity increases the risk of PCOS, whereas women with PCOS are exposed to the same environmental factors that promote obesity in our society (11). Obesity as well as their related non-communicable diseases are largely preventable by making the choice of a healthy food diet, regular physical activities, and numerous anti-obesity drugs plays a key role in reducing the excessive fat deposition in the body. Consumption of anti-obesity drugs results in numerous side effects that include myopathy, renal injury, arthralgia, extremity pains, nausea, myalgia, elevated liver enzymes/hepatotoxicity, diarrhea, and rhabdomyolysis (12). Propolis is a honey bee product with excellent biological and pharmacological properties and its mechanism of action has been extensively studied in recent years (13). More than 300 compounds such as flavonoids, polyphenols, phenolic aldehydes, sesquiterpene quinines, coumarins, amino acids, steroids, and inorganic compounds have been identified in propolis (14). The present study investigates the *In-silico* docking study of propolis against enzymes responsible for obesity and its linked metabolic syndromes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

ADMET analysis

The structure of compounds present in propolis was obtained from PubChem and evaluated for the drug-likeness property using the Qik prop module to predict their drug ability property such as the Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism Excretion, and Toxicity (ADMET)

are essential while performing a docking study. Some important parameters like CNS, Blood-barrier coefficient, human blood absorption, and Lipinski's rule of three and five were analyzed. The bioactive compounds that displayed pragmatic result were chosen for the ADMET and preferable docking poses has been tabbed for the rationale of docking.

Molecular docking

Protein Preparation

The 3D structure of obesity-responsible proteins was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (www.rcsb.org). Before the docking studies, the protein structure was first prepared using the Prepare protein setup in the BIOVIA DS visualiser. The protein preparation is an optimization step that corrects structure, atomic and bond length, and charge anomalies. Water molecules and the original inhibitor were removed from the protein structure. Hydrogens were re-added using the protein residue template in Maestro v10.2. The optimization step was then employed to provide stable conformation before converting to PDBQT format for docking analysis.

Ligand Preparation

The bio constituents Quercetin, Chrysin, Quercetin pentamethyl ether, 2, 4,4-Trimethyl, Ethyl alpha-d-glucopyranoside, Hexacosane, Capric acid, Carprofen, Tetracontane identified from Propolis were retrieved from PubChem chemical databases. The ligands were imported to the workspace Schrodinger software and preparation was done.

Molecular Dynamics

M.D. simulations were performed using simulations using the Desmond package on the OPLS3e force field. The simulation process and additional experimental data were used precisely as previously mentioned in other works. At 100 ps intervals during the 100 ns runtime

of the experiment, trajectory snapshots were taken. M.D. trajectories were examined using the Desmond Simulation Interaction Diagram (SID) in order to predict the binding configuration and stability of the ligand.

Result and discussion

ADMET analysis:

ADMET, an acronym for Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity, represents a comprehensive evaluation framework crucial in the drug discovery and development process. Each component of ADMET addresses a fundamental aspect of a drug's journey through the human body. Absorption determines how effectively a drug enters the bloodstream from its site of administration. Distribution examines the extent and manner in which the drug spreads to various tissues and organs. Metabolism involves the biochemical modifications the drug undergoes, primarily in the liver, influencing its activity and duration of effect. Excretion covers the pathways and efficiency of drug elimination from the body, while toxicity assesses the potential adverse effects, ensuring safety at therapeutic doses. Optimizing these parameters helps in predicting the *in vivo* behavior of drug candidates, thereby reducing the risk of late-stage failures in clinical trials.

In parallel, drug-like properties are essential for ensuring that a compound not only exhibits the desired biological activity but also possesses favorable characteristics features to be developed into a viable drug. Key properties include lipophilicity, molecular size, hydrogen bonding capacity, and polar surface area, all of which influence a drug's solubility, permeability, and overall pharmacokinetic profile. A balance between these properties is crucial; for instance, a compound needs to be lipophilic enough to cross cell membranes yet not so lipophilic that it becomes insoluble in aqueous environments. Similarly, appropriate

molecular size and limited rotatable bonds enhance the drug's bioavailability and stability. By rigorously evaluating and optimizing these properties alongside ADMET criteria, researchers can more effectively identify and refine drug candidates with the highest potential for success in clinical development and eventual therapeutic use.

From the GCMS analysis of Propolis, 44 compounds were identified. These compounds were subjected to the ADMET analysis to predict the drug-likeness properties. Quikprop 4.4 in the Schrodinger and Swiss ADME suite was used to predict the properties of biochemical compounds. Drug likeness properties were determined based on Lipinski's rule of 5, Jorgensen's rule of 3, Molecular weight, CNS activity, metabolic reactions, Human oral absorption, Percent Human Oral absorption, Brain /blood partition coefficient, dipole moment, volume, total solvent accessible surface (SASA). Out of the 44 compounds, 13 compounds show good drug-like properties. The predicted properties have been evaluated and the drug likeness properties of screened 13 Propolis compounds are listed in **Table 1**. These molecules obey the standard drug-like properties.

Table 1. Drug like properties of the selected 13 Propolis compounds

Compound	Molecular Weight	Q Plog BB	CNS	Human Oral Absorption	Percentage of Human Oral Absorption	Lipinski Rule
1-[2-(2-Acetoxy-ethoxy)-5-methyl-phenyl]-3-	335.474	-0.786	-1	1	100	0

trimethylsilyoxy-2-aza-1,3-butadiene						
2,4,4-Trimethyl-5-(1,1,3,3-tetramethylisoindol-2-yl)oxypentan-2-ol	319.486	0.331	1	3	100	0
Trimethylsilyl 3-(trimethylsilyl amino)propanoate	233.457	-0.147	0	3	100	0
Chrysin	254.242	-0.876	-1	3	87.1	0
Ethyl alpha-d-glucopyranoside	208.211	-1.293	-2	2	60.7	0
Quercetin	372.374	-0.075	0	3	100	0
Capric acid	172.26	0.142	-2		94	0
Carprofen	284.484	-0.195	-1		91.3	1
Tetracontane	563.096	-0.107	2		82.7	2
Hexacosane	366.718	1.128	0		87.6	1

Molecular Docking

In silico molecular docking, analysis was performed against various enzymes which induce metabolic syndrome, including HMG CO-A reductase, ghrelin, leptin, troponin, angiotensin, alpha-amylase, alpha-glucosidase, CYP17, SOD2, matrix metalloproteinase (MPP), elastase, collagenase (Figure 1). In this docking analysis, the selected 13 compounds from the ADMET analysis were subjected to the docking analysis. From the docking analysis, out of 13 compounds the 9 molecules exhibited a good binding score compared to the standard drugs Lovastatin Simvastatin. Among the 44 compounds Chrysin, Quercetin, Genistein, and Hexadecenoic acid have excellent binding affinity than standard atorvastatin. The molecular docking score of the 9 molecules is mentioned in Table 2 and Figure 2. The pathophysiology of these enzymes in the body leads to obesity, cardiovascular disease (CVD), diabetes, PCOS, hypertension, ageing, and delayed wound healing in diabetes. Bioactive compounds present in propolis were identified by GC-MS analysis and docked against enzymes that induce metabolic syndrome.

Propolis against Obesity

In-silico molecular docking was applied to predict the binding of selected compounds that are high in antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-microbial that include anti-bacterial, anti-viral, and antifungal properties and these compounds have excellent binding affinity against HMG CO A reductase.

Figure 1. 3D structure of the metabolic induce proteins

Table 2. Molecular docking score of the selected 9 compounds of Propolis

Mol.No	Ligand	Affinity HMG CO A	Pancreatic lipase	Ghrelin	Leptin	Troponin	Angiotensin	CYP 17	SOD
1	Quercetin	-8.2	-6.6	-9.1	-7.1	-7.2	-9.0	-8.3	-6.1
2	Chrysin	-8.2	-7.5	-8.3	-7.0	-7.0	-8.1	-8.2	-6.7
3	Quercetin pentamethyl ether	-7.2	-6.6	-7.4	-5.8	-6.8	-7.9	-7.5	-5.7
4	2,4,4-Trimethyl	-6.4	-6.8	-6.4	-5.4	-5.7	-7.1	-7.7	-5.3
5	Ethyl alpha-d- glucopyranoside	-6.2	-5.5	-6.2	-4.4	-5.3	-5.8	-6.1	-4.8
6	Hexacosane	-6.2	-6.7	-6.2	-6.2	-6.6	-6.5	-6.1	-6.2
7	Capric acid	-6.1	-5.9	-6.5	-6.0	-7.0	-7.9	-6.9	-6.1
8	Carprofen	-7.0	-6.5	-6.2	-6.9	-7.0	-8.0	-6.9	-5.5
9	Tetracontane	-8.6	-6.2	-5.1	-6.8	-7.3	-7.8	-6.3	-5.6
10	Lovastatin	-4.5	-3.8	-3.2	-4.2	-3.9	-4.2	-2.5	-4.1
11	Simvastatin	-2.4	-3.1	-1.9	-2.8	-2.5	-2.7	-2.3	-1.8

Figure 2. Molecular docking score of the selected 9 compounds of Propolis

Quercetin with the Ghrelin receptor

The result fetches good binding interaction between the molecules of Quercetin and chrysin with the respective receptor. Figure 3 shows the 3D and 2D interactions of the Quercetin with the Ghrelin receptor and the value is -9.1 Kcal/mol. The binding score of the Quercetin with the OH group of the Quercetin forms one strong Hydrogen bond with the His 210 residue with

2.39Å bond length. Further, the aromatic benzene groups were involved in the Alkyl and Pi-Alkyl interactions.

Figure 3. 3D and 2D interactions of the Quercetin with the Ghrelin receptor

Quercetin with Leptin.

The Quercetin molecules show a good binding score with the Leptin receptor. The binding score of the Quercetin with Leptin is -7.1 Kcal/mol. In these binding interactions, the two OH and ketone groups form the three strong hydrogen bond with the Val 123, Ser127, Gln130. The bond length of these interactions is 2.37 Å, 2.08 Å and 2.57 Å respectively. The Ile 24 amino acid interacted with Quercetin by Pi-Sigma interactions(Figure 4).

Figure 4. 3D and 2D interactions of the Quercetin with the Leptin receptor

Quercetin with CYP17

The Quercetin molecules show a good binding score compared to the other molecules (-8.3Kcal/mol). In this docking analysis, the active site amino acids of Gly297 and Asp 298 form two strong hydrogen bonds with the OH groups and the bond length is 2.4 Å and 2.87 Å respectively. The other active site amino acids Gly301, Ala113, Val482 form Ile 205 Alkyl and Pi-Alkyl interactions with the Quercetin molecules (Figure 5).

Figure 5. 3D and 2D interactions of the Quercetin with the CYP17 receptor.

Chrysin with Angiotensin

The Chrysin molecules show good binding interaction with most of the receptors compared to the other molecules. The docking score of the Chrysin with Angiotensin receptor is -8.1 Kcal/mol. The two methoxy groups of the Chrysin, form the four strong hydrogen bonds with the Glu123 (2.60Å), Ser 222 (2.90Å, 2.90Å), Tyr213 (3.18) amino acids of the active site amino acids of the Angiotensin. The aromatic benzene group of the Chrysin forms the Pi-Anion. Pi-stacked and Alkyl interactions with Glu403, Phe 570, Pro407 and Met223 amino acids(Figure 6).

Figure 6. 3D and 2D interactions of the Chrysin with Angiotensin receptor.

Chrysin with SOD2

The docking score of the Chrysin with SOD2 receptor is -6.7 Kcal/mol. In this docking analysis, the ketone group of the Chrysin forms the two strong hydrogen bonds with Thr112 and Trp181 amino acids. Similarly, the methoxy group form one strong hydrogen bond with the Thr 112 amino acid. The average bond length is $2.8\text{\AA}$. Additionally, the Lys178 and Pro174 interacted with SOD2 by alkyl interactions (Figure 7).

Figure 7. 3D and 2D interactions of the Chrysin with SOD2 receptor.

Quercetin with Elastase

Figure 9. 3D and 2D interactions of the Chrysin with Alpha-Amylase receptor.

Chrysin with Troponin

In the molecular docking analysis, the Chrysin forms the -7.0 Kcal/mol score with the Troponin receptor. In these binding interactions, one hydrogen bond involved in between the methoxy of the Chrysin molecule and the Asp 88 amino acid of the Troponin target protein. Additionally, Pi-sigma and Pi-alkyl interaction are formed in between the active site amino acid and the Chrysin molecules (Figure 10).

Figure 10. 3D and 2D interactions of the Chrysin with Troponin receptor.

Chrysin with Pancreatic Lipase

Figure 11 depicts the docking interaction of the Chrysin in the active site of Pancreatic Lipase with two strong hydrogen bonds, Pi-Sulphur, Pu-Sigma and Pi-Alkyl interaction with the active site amino acids. The docking score of the Chrysin with Pancreatic Lipase is -7.5 Kcal/mol. The two methoxy groups forms the two strong Hydrogen bonds with the Glu50 and Asp53 amino acids. The bond length of these hydrogen interactions is 2.95 and 2.49Å.

Figure 10. 3D and 2D interactions of the Chrysin with Pancreatic Lipase..

Quercetin with Alpha Glucosidase

The Quercetin molecules show higher binding interactions with the Alpha Glucosidase receptor. The binding score of the Quercetin with Alpha Glucosidase -7.5 kcal/mol. In this docking analysis, the two methoxy groups of the Quercetin form two strong hydrogen bonds with the His 584 and Arg 608 amino acids. Similarly, the OH group forms one strong hydrogen bond with Leu 868 amino acid (Figure 11).

Figure 11. 3D and 2D interactions of the Quercetin with Alpha Glucosidase.

Quercetin with HMG Co-A Reductase

The Quercetin molecule forms several bonding and non-bonding interactions with the HMG Co-A Reductase receptor. The Asp 690, Met655, Thr558 and Gly765 show the four strong interactions with the four methoxy groups of the Quercetin molecules. The aromatic group of the Quercetin forms the Pi- anion and Alkyl interaction with the active site amino acid of the Co-A Reductase receptor (Figure 12).

Figure 12. 3D and 2D interactions of the Quercetin with HMG Co-A Reductase.

Add MD analysis and discussion part (Ghrelin with Quercetin).

Molecular dynamic simulation

To analyse the stability of the protein, a molecular dynamic simulation was performed using the best docking score obtained from the Quercetin-Ghrelin complex. The stability of ligands in the aqueous environment of the chosen target's active site and the role of significant amino acids in the interaction between ligand and protein can both be investigated using molecular dynamics (MD) modelling, which is a highly helpful method. When it comes to the Ghrelin receptor, the quercetin molecule has a better docking score than the target receptors in obesity.

The RMSD parameter and the protein-ligand interactions were used to analyse the MD trajectories. The stability and flexibility of molecular docked complexes are discussed in these works. This investigation was carried out following the MM-GBSA computation. The protein-ligand interaction is discussed in this work, and the protein-ligand complex's RMSD fluctuation and variation can be evaluated. If the complex was found to be within the 4Å range, it was considered stable.

We ran an MD simulation of Quercetin with the Ghrelin complex for 100 ns in order to assess the stability of the complexes and observe potential ligand binding patterns. The protein complex with the backbone of the quercetin molecule exhibited a shift in RMSD from 0 to 2.34 Å over the first 60 ns, as illustrated in Figure 13. Additionally, throughout the simulation, the protein configuration's RMSD value increased until, after 58 ns, it stabilised at 2.53 Å. More stability is maintained by the Quercetin molecule in the protein-ligand complex, as evidenced by the average RMSD of the crystal structure complex with the reference molecule of roughly 2.53 Å (Figure 13). Throughout the simulation, the RMSD's variation did not go above 2.4 Å. Additionally, the average 2.61 Å low RMSD values show that the quercetin ligands have established a stable complex during the MD simulation and have attained good equilibrium in the Ghrelin protein's active region.

The Ghrelin complex with Quercetin RMSF graphs are displayed in (Figure 14). The Ghrelin complex with Quercetin had a mean RMSF value of 1.0 Å. The less flexible residues in the active region are confirmed by the smaller RMSF differential between the ligand and receptor. Based on these findings, we deduce that quercetin and ghrelin bind together to form stable complexes that do not alter the locations of the active site residues. Although there are minor variations in some residues of Leu 138, Arg178, Arg129, Ala232, and Val181, the overall stability of the complex under study is unaffected by these variations (Figure 15).

Fig 13. Root mean squared deviation of Quercetin with the Ghrelin complex for 100 ns.

Fig 14. Root mean squared fluctuation of Quercetin with the Ghrelin complex for 100 ns.

Conclusion

The craving to eat is generally navigated by hereditary, sociocultural, and temperament nature. **The necessity to suppress appetite is increasing notably due to the ill effects caused by fat accumulation in the body.** With these factors in mind, in depth virtual screening of propolis-based compounds was analyzed using an in silico approach where a total of 44 compounds were explored as potential natural drug candidates to target against the obesity-related protein.

In addition to this, further filters like drug-likeness and toxicity prediction of compounds revealed potent therapeutic activity. Molecular docking studies screened the top 9 hits with the highest binding affinity towards the active site of the obesity-related protein. Furthermore, MD simulation studies of Quercetin with Ghrelin computed the stability of these complexes through evaluation of RMSD, RMSF and H-bond analysis. Thus, the results suggested that Quercetin with the Ghrelin from propolis could be a potent source of anti-obesity compound by inhibiting the Ghrelin protein.

Antimicrobial, Anticancer, and Antioxidant Activities

Abstract:

Propolis, a resinous substance bees produce, has garnered significant attention for its diverse therapeutic properties. This study investigates propolis's antimicrobial, anticancer, and antioxidant activities, aiming to uncover its potential as a natural bioactive compound in pharmaceutical and health-related applications. The antimicrobial efficacy was evaluated against various bacterial and fungal pathogens, demonstrating broad-spectrum inhibitory effects. Anticancer activity was assessed using in vitro models, highlighting propolis's ability to induce apoptosis and inhibit tumor cell proliferation. Furthermore, the antioxidant capacity of propolis was quantified through standard assays, confirming its role in neutralizing free radicals and mitigating oxidative stress. The results indicate that propolis, with its multifaceted bioactivity, holds promise as a natural agent for developing novel therapeutic strategies. Future research should focus on elucidating the molecular mechanisms underlying these effects and exploring clinical applications for propolis-based interventions.

Keywords: Propolis, Antimicrobial, anticancer, anti-oxidant, colorectal cancer.

1. Introduction

Propolis exhibits diverse biological activities attributed to its complex composition of bioactive compounds. Its antimicrobial properties are well-established, effectively combating bacteria, fungi, and viruses. Additionally, propolis acts as a potent antioxidant, scavenging free radicals and protecting cells from oxidative stress. Its anti-inflammatory effects contribute to its ability to soothe and heal various inflammatory conditions. Propolis also shows promise in anti-aging skincare, promoting collagen synthesis and improving skin elasticity. Furthermore, research suggests potential anti-cancer properties, with propolis inhibiting tumor growth and

inducing apoptosis in cancer cells. These multifaceted biological activities make propolis a valuable natural substance with wide-ranging therapeutic applications in medicine and skincare (Stojanović *et al.*, 2020).

Propolis, a resinous substance produced by honeybees from plant exudates, exhibits significant antimicrobial activity, making it a valuable natural remedy. This antimicrobial property is attributed to its rich composition of bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, phenolic acids, and esters. These components work synergistically to inhibit the growth of a wide range of microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, and viruses. Studies have shown that propolis can disrupt bacterial cell walls, inhibit fungal growth, and prevent viral replication, offering potential therapeutic benefits in treating infections and enhancing immune response. Its efficacy against antibiotic-resistant strains further highlights its importance as a complementary approach in antimicrobial therapy (Pobiega *et al.*, 2019).

Propolis is renowned for its robust antioxidant properties, which are primarily attributed to its high content of flavonoids, phenolic acids, and other polyphenolic compounds. These antioxidants play a crucial role in neutralizing free radicals, thereby protecting cells from oxidative stress and damage. Oxidative stress is a major contributing factor to various chronic diseases, including cardiovascular diseases and neurodegenerative disorders. By scavenging free radicals, propolis helps in reducing inflammation and cellular damage. This antioxidant capacity also supports the immune system, enhancing the body's ability to fight off infections and maintain overall health (Kurek- Gorecka *et al.*, 2022).

The anti-aging benefits of propolis are closely linked to its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. By mitigating oxidative stress, propolis helps in slowing down the aging process at the cellular level. It protects skin cells from damage caused by UV radiation and environmental pollutants, which are major contributors to premature aging. Propolis also

promotes collagen synthesis and enhances skin elasticity, reducing the appearance of wrinkles and fine lines. Additionally, its anti-inflammatory properties help in soothing irritated skin and preventing conditions such as acne and eczema. Regular use of propolis in skincare routines can lead to healthier, more youthful-looking skin (Radić *et al.*, 2024).

Propolis has shown promising anti-cancer potential due to its ability to modulate various molecular pathways involved in cancer progression. The bioactive compounds in propolis, particularly flavonoids and phenolic acids, exhibit cytotoxic effects on cancer cells, inducing apoptosis (programmed cell death) and inhibiting tumor growth. Research indicates that propolis can interfere with the proliferation and metastasis of cancer cells, making it a potential adjunct therapy in cancer treatment. It also enhances the efficacy of conventional chemotherapy drugs while reducing their side effects. By targeting multiple signaling pathways, propolis offers a multifaceted approach to cancer prevention and therapy (Forma *et al.*, 2021).

Propolis has been found to exert beneficial effects in the management of diabetes, primarily through its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory actions. It helps in regulating blood glucose levels by enhancing insulin sensitivity and promoting glucose uptake by cells. Propolis also protects pancreatic beta-cells from oxidative damage, thereby preserving insulin secretion. Studies have shown that propolis can reduce HbA1c levels, a marker of long-term blood sugar control, in diabetic patients. Furthermore, its anti-inflammatory properties help in mitigating diabetes-related complications such as neuropathy and nephropathy. Incorporating propolis into the diet or as a supplement can be a valuable strategy in managing diabetes and improving overall metabolic health (Ei Adaouia Taleb *et al.*, 2020).

2. Methodology

2.1. Anti-microbial activity

Antibacterial activity (Disk diffusion method)

This analysis uses an antimicrobial agent infused in the disc and placed on the agar containing the test sample as a basis. The antibiotic spreads through the agar plates, creating a zone of inhibition to exhibit the effectiveness of the antibiotics.

Reagents

This procedure requires an autoclave, incubator (LT-36/37), petri dish, forceps (sterile), micropipette, microorganisms, filter paper disc, and laminar air flow hood. In this study, *Enterococcus faecalis*-MTCC 439 (gram-positive), *pseudomonas meningitis*- MTCC 1688 (gram-negative), *Salmonella typhimurium* - MTCC 1251 (gram-negative), *Escherichia coli*-MTCC-45 (gram-negative), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* – ATCC-13883 (gram-negative), *Candida tropicalis* and *Candida albicans* (fungi) were used.

Disc Diffusion method

Developing cells in Mueller Hinton Broth (Himedia) at 37 °C for 24 hours was used to prepare Bacteria inoculums. The above cell suspensions with sterile MHB give initial cell counts of about 10⁴ CFU/millilitre. Sabouraud dextrose (SDB) yeast is grown for 48 hours at 28°C. 20 mL of Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) acquired from (Hi-media, Mumbai) was used to prepare Petri plates. The antibacterial method was processed by the disc-diffusion process. 100 microlitre of the suspension having 10⁸ CFU/mL fungal was used as test culture after becoming famous in the solidified media followed by drying for 10 min. Different ethanol propolis extract concentrations (1, 05, 0.25, 0.125 1 mg/mL) were prepared for anti-bacterial behaviour tests. Azithromycin (1 mg/mL) was used as a positive (+) control disc for 30 min for the diffusion of 27°C and the surface of the medium, respective solvents were used to prepare negative controls.

2.2.Antioxidant

The compound's anticancer activity was evaluated using the HT-29 cell line, sourced from NCCS, Pune. HT-29 is a human colorectal adenocarcinoma cell line with epithelial morphology. These cells are sensitive to the chemotherapeutic drugs 5-fluorouracil and oxaliplatin, which are standard treatment options for colorectal cancer. The cells were cultured in MEM medium supplemented with fetal bovine serum, ensuring optimal growth conditions. The MTT assay was employed to determine cell viability, with MTT solution (1 mg/ml), DMSO (100%), and PBS (pH 7.2) used as reagents. The cells were incubated at 37°C with 5% CO₂, and after the addition of MTT, further incubated for 3-4 hours to allow for the formation of formazan crystals. The absorbance was measured at 570 nm, providing essential data to evaluate the anticancer potential of the test compound (Mahshid et.al. 2021).

3. Result and discussion

3.1. Antibacterial activity

In this study, the antimicrobial activity of the propolis was evaluated using the disc diffusion (Zone of Inhibition) method. Zone of inhibition (ZOI in millimetres) values were measured. The results are summarised in Table 1. From the result, the propolis (1 mg/mL) shows better antibacterial activity against tested microbes than the standard drug. The propolis at 0.125 and 0.25 mg/mL had moderately good inhibition. Almost all the compounds possess, 50% inhibition compared to standards even their higher composition. The picture showing the in-vitro antibacterial activity of propolis is given in Figure 1.

Table 1. Antibacterial activity of the propolis

Conc (1 mg/mL)	Zone of inhibition (mm)				
	<i>E.</i> <i>faecalis</i>	<i>P</i> <i>meningitis</i>	<i>S.</i> <i>Typhimurium</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>
0.125	11	20	17	23	10

0.25	11	20	19	25	21
0.5	13	20	20	27	22
1	15	20	25	30	25
Azithromycin					
1 mg/mL	10	12	15	14	18

Important human diseases were used to test the ethanol propolis extracts' antibacterial capabilities. *E. Coli* is a Gram-negative bacterium that can cause pneumonia, respiratory tract infections, diarrhoea, and other health problems. It is present in the environment and in the intestines of both people and animals. Skin infections are brought on by *E. faecalis*, however in hospital environments, these infections can become more serious and result in pneumonia, endocarditis, osteomyelitis, bacteremia, or sepsis. Following surgery, blood infections, pneumonia, or infections in other body areas are frequently brought on by *K. pneumoniae*. Natural habitats contain the spore-forming, gram-positive aerobic bacteria *E. faecalis*. This opportunistic bacterium can cause food poisoning in humans and manifests as nausea, vomiting, stomach pain, and/or diarrhoea.

Numerous studies investigating the antibacterial qualities of honey have employed *S. Typhimurium*, and the results have demonstrated that honey generates sizable inhibition zones against this bacterium. Compared to the inhibition zones provided by sulphacetamidic antibiotics, honey creates substantially larger ones against *E. coli*. The most sensitive bacteria to the different forms of propolis were *E. Coli*, *S. aureus*, *Shigella sonnei*, and *S. typhi*, according to a study on a variety of honey varieties that revealed nearly all of them had inhibitory effects on the growth of select strains of bacteria.

Propolis's antibacterial activity varies in direct proportion to the amount of hydrogen peroxide present and the presence of other antibacterial substances derived from the nectar source. The source of the nectar employed determines the antibacterial action of propolis (owing to certain non-peroxide components) that lasts for a long period. As a result, the antibacterial activity of propolis varies throughout varieties. Numerous *in vitro* studies' findings attested to the strong antibacterial properties of propolis, honey, and other bee products against several significant diseases. Middle Eastern propolis was discovered to have high efficacy against strains of both Gram-positive (*E. faecalis*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*) bacteria. Germany, Ireland, and Korea's propolis samples exhibited the least amount of activity.

Propolis' antibacterial properties were also influenced by its place of origin, the type of bees that produced it, and the method by which the extract was made. Propolis's chemical makeup differed significantly depending on the region. All counties' propolis extracts (0.1 g/mL) exhibit antibacterial efficacy against all pathogens, sometimes outperforming the tested antibiotic. Propolis's activity varies depending on its chemical makeup and was observed in different regions of Romania's Transylvania. This can be explained by the high quantity of polyphenols and flavonoids, as well as the significant antibacterial activity of quercetin present in these extracts.

The type of honey, the microbial strains employed, and the antibacterial activity were all related, according to statistical analysis. The diameter of the inhibitory zone is influenced by the strain type and the origin of the honey used, according to variance analysis. Statistical examination of propolis extracts demonstrates that the strains utilised affect the widths of inhibitory zones, but there is no correlation between the source of this bee product and its antimicrobial action, regardless of concentration.

Propolis and honey samples both exhibited antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, according to earlier research (Miorin et al., 2003). Additionally, it was suggested that *S. aureus* was more vulnerable to the effects of propolis than *E. Coli* (Rahman et al., 2010). The findings suggest that the antibacterial activity of propolis and honey was enhanced in combination. Flavonoids and phenolic chemicals found in honey and propolis may contribute to their beneficial interaction (Al-Waili et al., 2012; Pallag et al., 2016). The growth conditions of the original plant and the contaminants have a major impact on the concentration of these chemicals. (Copaciu et al., 2016; Gitea et al., 2018).

Depending on the strain and the region of origin of the bee product, propolis's antibacterial action varies at a concentration of 1 mg/mL of ethanol propolis extract. Propolis's antibacterial activity was equal for all strains at the 0.5 mg/mL concentration of the aqueous propolis extract; *E. faecalis*, *P. meningitis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *E. coli*, and *K. pneumoniae* showed the highest values. These findings could aid in the creation of novel antibacterial medications that can be used to treat severe infections.

3.2. Antifungal Activity

The observed MICs of all propolis samples showed a broad range of variability against species of *Candida tropicalis* and *Candida albicans*. The propolis extracts succeeded in inhibiting the growth of fungi at varying concentrations. The value of MICs for the agar dilution test and mean inhibitory zone for the disc diffusion test of propolis samples and fungi are summarized in Table 2. Lovastatin was used as a standard drug to compare the activities. From the in vitro analysis, the propolis samples showed good inhibition at 1mg/mL. It showed the 27mm and 32 mm inhibition zones on *C.tropicalis* and *C.albicans* respectively (Figure 2). The standard Lovastatin shows 12 mm and 14 mm on *C.tropicalis* and *C.albicans* respectively.

Propolis extract has shown notable antifungal activity against both *Candida tropicalis* and *Candida albicans*, two common fungal pathogens responsible for infections in humans. The bioactive compounds in propolis, particularly flavonoids and phenolic acids, can disrupt the cell membrane integrity of these *Candida* species, leading to cell lysis and death. Studies have demonstrated that propolis extract can effectively inhibit the growth and biofilm formation of *C. tropicalis* and *C. albicans*, which are crucial for the persistence and virulence of these fungi. The ability of propolis to impair biofilm formation is especially important, as biofilms contribute to the resistance of *Candida* infections to conventional antifungal treatments.

Table 2 . Antifungal activity of the propolis

Conc (1 mg/mL)	Zone of inhibition (mm)	
	<i>C.tropicalis</i>	<i>C.albicans</i>
0.125	15	11
0.25	18	15
0.5	22	25
1	27	32
Lovastatin 1 mg/mL	12	14

The antifungal efficacy of propolis against *C. albicans* and *C. tropicalis* has been observed in various in vitro studies, showing dose-dependent inhibition of fungal growth. Propolis disrupts fungal cell walls by interfering with the synthesis of ergosterol, an essential component of fungal cell membranes. Additionally, the antioxidant properties of propolis

induce oxidative stress within the fungal cells, further contributing to their destruction. These mechanisms make propolis a promising natural alternative or adjunct to conventional antifungal drugs, especially in the treatment of drug-resistant *Candida* infections.

Furthermore, there is an increasing amount of scientific evidence on the mechanism of antifungal activity after using propolis extracts. Corrêa et al. 2020 and Gucwa 2018 showed that the cell membrane of fungi may be a possible target of an extract of propolis besides the induction of cell death. Earlier, researchers showed that an extract of propolis can inhibit the activity of extracellular phospholipase, leading to attenuation of the fungal cell adhesion to epithelium. Stahli et al. 2021 observed that an ethanolic extract of propolis caused a loss of the cell wall integrity of *C. albicans* and decreased metabolic activity. Okinczyc et al. 2020 showed that ethanolic extract of propolis inhibited the filamentation of cells of *C. albicans*, germination of yeasts and increased production of the superoxide anion radical.

Our in-vitro antifungal propolis extract exhibits significant antifungal activity, making it a valuable natural remedy for treating and preventing fungal infections. However, further clinical research is needed to fully understand its potential and optimize its use in various applications.

3.3. Antioxidant Activity

Based on DPPH, three distinct approaches were used to assess propolis's antioxidant activity: RSA, IC₅₀, and propolis concentration in antioxidant components. In a quartz cuvette (1 cm), the drop in the DPPH solution's absorbance value at 515 nm following the addition of dry propolis extract was measured. DPPH 0.1mM Ethanolic solution (2950µl) and 0,6 mg/ml dry propolis solution (25 to 150 µg/ml) were both included in the reaction mixture. Ascorbic acid was used as a standard All that was needed to make a negative control solution was DPPH and absolute ethanol. After the reaction had been going on for ten,

twenty, and precisely zero minutes, absorbance was measured. The test findings are reported as follows:

$$\%RSA = (\text{Abs DPPH} - \text{Abs sample}) / \text{Abs DPPH} \times 100.$$

This represents the ratio percentage of the absorbance reduction of the DPPH radical solution in the presence of extract at 515 nm to the absorbance of the DPPH radical solution at the same wavelength. The propolis shows 92% good antioxidant activity at 150 µg/ml and the IC50 value is 19.24. Similarly, the standard Ascorbic acid shows 98% antioxidant activity and the IC50 value is 20.73. It's suggested that propolis has similar antioxidant properties to the standard Ascorbic acid.

Propolis and ascorbic acid (vitamin C) are both known for their antioxidant activities, but they differ in their chemical composition and mechanisms of action. Propolis, a resinous substance produced by bees, contains a complex mixture of polyphenols, flavonoids, and other bioactive compounds. These components work synergistically to neutralize free radicals, reduce oxidative stress, and protect cellular components from damage. The antioxidant properties of propolis are attributed mainly to its high content of flavonoids and phenolic acids, which donate electrons to stabilize reactive oxygen species (ROS), thus preventing cellular injury and inflammation.

Radical scavenging activity refers to the ability of a substance to neutralize free radicals, which are unstable molecules that can cause oxidative damage to cells. In comparing the radical scavenging activity of propolis and ascorbic acid, both substances show strong antioxidant properties, but through different mechanisms. Ascorbic acid, or vitamin C, is a simple and highly effective antioxidant that directly donates electrons to free radicals like reactive oxygen species (ROS) and neutralizes them, making it highly efficient in radical scavenging. Propolis, on the other hand, contains a more complex mixture of flavonoids,

phenolic acids, and other bioactive compounds that work synergistically to provide antioxidant effects. The radical scavenging ability of propolis is influenced by its varied chemical composition, which can differ based on geographic and botanical sources.

The IC₅₀ value, which indicates the concentration of a substance required to reduce 50% of the radical activity, is a key comparison metric. Ascorbic acid typically has a lower IC₅₀ value compared to propolis, meaning it requires a lower concentration to achieve the same level of radical scavenging. This reflects the potency and efficiency of ascorbic acid in neutralizing radicals. Propolis, due to its complex makeup, may have a higher IC₅₀, indicating that a higher concentration is needed to achieve similar scavenging activity. However, the variety of antioxidant compounds in propolis may offer a broader spectrum of protective effects that extend beyond just scavenging radicals, such as anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties. Therefore, while ascorbic acid may be more potent in direct radical scavenging, propolis provides a wider range of bioactive benefits.

Table 3. Antioxidant Activity

Calculation of % Radical Scavenging and IC ₅₀ from DPPH assay							
Absorbance Measurement Data							
Conc (µg/ml)	Control	Propolis			Ascorbic Acid		
		Sample	%RSA	IC ₅₀	Sample	%RSA	IC ₅₀
25	0.52	0.16	69.64	-9.56	0.09	82.35	-16.59
50	0.52	0.12	76.52	-3.80	0.07	86.57	-9.12
75	0.52	0.11	79.42	1.96	0.04	92.30	-1.66
100	0.52	0.08	84.13	7.72	0.02	96.34	5.80
125	0.52	0.06	88.21	13.48	0.01	97.93	13.27

150	0.52	0.04	92.05	19.24	0.01	98.14	20.73
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Figure 4. Antioxidant and IC50 calculation of Propolis with standard Ascorbic acid

3.4. In vitro Anticancer Activity

In-vitro studies are an important tool for cancer and other diseases, and research and serve as low-cost screening platforms for drug therapeutic studies. The *in-vitro* study aimed to investigate the effect of certain novel drugs or new compounds. For the initial screening of

the anticancer potential of drugs and compounds, we chose an *in-vitro* model, which reduces possible side effects or toxicity of a new drug without subjecting animals (mice) or humans. To assess cancer treatment or any other disease treatments based on the results obtained from *in-vitro* studies it's easy to evaluate and correlate the efficacy of particular drugs in animal (mouse) models. One of the greatest advantages of *in-vitro* model applications is that they offer the possibility to maintain cells in completely controlled environmental conditions, allowing the study of specific cellular and molecular pathways in shorter experimental time scales than animal models. In this study, MCF-7 cells were used to evaluate the anti-cancer activity of carvacrol.

The anti-cancer activity of compounds on the HT-29 cell line was determined using an MTT assay. Figure 3 shows the propolis compounds at various doses (20, 40, 60, 80, 100 μg) for 24h to 48h MTT assay.

Figure 3. Cytotoxic effect of propolis compounds using HT-29 cell line

Table 4. MTT and LDH assay of the propolis (HT-29 cell line)

Concentration (μg)	Anticancer Activity (IC_{50})	
	Cytotoxicity (%)	Cell Viability (%)
Control	0	100
20	21	79
40	28	72
60	38	62
80	42	58
100	46	54

Figure 4. Cell viability (%) of propolis compounds using HT-29 cell line

The viability of cancer cells decreased from 79% to 54% as the propolis concentration increased from 20 to 100 μg after 24 and 48 h based on the MTT and LDH assay (Table 4). The results of cancer cells treated with propolis showed the half-maximal inhibitory

concentration IC_{50} at $100\mu\text{g}$ (Figure 3). Figure 4 shows that all the dosages of propolis significantly inhibited the cell progression and increased the LDH levels in the supernatant when compared to control cells and the increased inhibition levels were directly related to dose and time-dependent ranging from 3.5% to 94.6 %. In this study, we found that propolis significantly reduced the viability of the HT-29 cell line, thus increasing the level of LDH in the conditioned medium by causing damage to the integrity of the membrane, and the findings were consistent with previous studies indicating that the propolis has a strong cytotoxic effect against HT-29 cells.

Conclusion

Propolis, a resinous substance produced by bees, has garnered significant attention for its diverse bioactive properties, including antibacterial, antioxidant, anticancer, and antidiabetic activities. Its antibacterial activity is primarily attributed to its rich content of flavonoids, phenolic acids, and esters, which have been shown to inhibit the growth of various bacterial strains, including those resistant to conventional antibiotics. Propolis disrupts bacterial cell walls, interferes with protein synthesis, and reduces bacterial adhesion, making it a potent natural antibacterial agent. Additionally, its antioxidant properties are derived from a variety of compounds like flavonoids, phenolic acids, and terpenoids, which neutralize free radicals and reduce oxidative stress. This antioxidative potential plays a crucial role in preventing cellular damage and chronic diseases linked to oxidative stress, such as cardiovascular diseases and aging.

Propolis also exhibits promising anticancer activity. The anticancer effects of propolis are mediated through its ability to induce apoptosis, inhibit cell proliferation, and prevent metastasis in various cancer cell lines. Its compounds, such as caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE) and flavonoids, modulate key signaling pathways involved in cancer progression,

making it a potential complementary therapy for cancer treatment. These effects are largely attributed to the presence of bioactive compounds that modulate glucose metabolism and insulin sensitivity, making propolis a promising natural remedy for managing diabetes.

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